

Multimodal DNN Certification for Image–Contour Representations under Projective Transformations

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Résumé Deep neural networks (DNNs) achieve remarkable performance in object recognition tasks. However, their robustness against realistic geometric perturbations, especially those induced by 3D viewpoint variations and projective transformations, remains limited. While most certification methods focus on additive pixel-wise perturbations, structured geometric attacks remain underexplored, particularly for contour classifiers. This paper presents a multimodal certification framework for object recognition combining image and contour representations under 3D–2D projective transformations. The proposed approach relies on abstract interpretation and extends the DeepPoly abstract domain to model projective attacks acting on planar contours through the group $PSL(2, \mathbb{C})$. Furthermore, we introduce a comparative analysis of contour reparameterization strategies, demonstrating that affine reparameterization significantly reduces certification conservativeness under projective distortions.

Keywords : Deep Neural Networks, Formal Verification, Abstract Interpretation, Projective Transformations, Contour Classification, DNN Robustness.

1 Introduction

Deep neural networks are widely deployed in safety-critical applications such as autonomous driving [1], robotics [10], and medical diagnosis [2]. Despite their strong empirical performance, they remain vulnerable to adversarial perturbations.

Several verification frameworks have been proposed, including linear programming approaches [17], linear relaxation methods [18], and abstract interpretation, which provides a theoretical foundation for computing sound over-approximations of reachable states in complex systems [3]. This approach has been successfully adapted for DNN certification [5], with DeepPoly [14] offering scalable and tight abstractions. However, existing works mainly address pixel-based models and primarily focus on

ℓ_p -norm-bounded additive perturbations, such as brightness variations [5], 3D rotations [13], and convolutional attacks [11] listed in Table 1.

DNN Certification with DeepPoly			
Image-based Models		Contour-based Models	
Attacks	References	Attacks	References
FGSM	[5]	2D Translation	[8]
2D Rotation	[14]	2D Rotation	[8]
Convolution	[11]	Convolution	[16,9]
3D Rotation	[13]	3D Rotation	AI3D[15]
–	–	3D Translation	AI3D[15]

Table 1. DNN certification using DeepPoly under different attack types : Image-based vs. Contour-based models

However, real-world perturbations are often geometric in nature, resulting from camera motion, object displacement, or viewpoint changes. In particular, 3D rigid transformations followed by perspective projection generate projective distortions in the image plane that cannot be adequately captured by simple additive noise models. With the emergence of deep contour classification architectures such as ContourCNN [4] and DeepGCSS [12], dedicated certification methods for contour representations are needed.

This paper introduces a multimodal certification framework combining image and contour representations under 3D–2D projective attacks. We extend DeepPoly to geometric transformations modeled via $PSL(2, \mathbb{C})$ and demonstrate that affine contour reparameterization significantly tightens certification bounds compared to arc-length normalization.

2 Proposed method

We introduce an abstract interpretation based approach for DNN verification across two modalities. The proposed framework incorporates two complementary verifiers to evaluate robustness in both image and contour classification under projective transformations see Figure 1.

2.1 Abstract domains for DNN certification under projective attacks

In this work, we leverage the DeepPoly abstract domain, which over-approximates neural network activations using linear constraints.

Figure 1. Multimodal System for DNN Verification against Projective transformation (image and contours)

Given an input region $R_{\bar{X}, \epsilon}$ around a nominal input \bar{X} , the robustness property holds if : $C_L = \{\bar{y} \in \bar{Y} \mid \arg \max \bar{y}_i = L\}$

where all outputs corresponding to perturbed inputs remain in class L .

A planar contour $\Gamma = \{z \mid z = y + ix\}$ undergoing a 3D rigid motion followed by perspective projection can be modeled through projective transformations.

The group of projective transformations is defined as :

$$\mathcal{PSL}(2, \mathbb{C}) = \frac{\mathcal{SL}(2, \mathbb{C})}{\pm Id} \quad (1)$$

where : $\mathcal{SL}(2, \mathbb{C}) = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} : ad - bc = 1 \right\}$. The action on the image plane is given by the linear fractional transformation : $z' = \frac{dz+c}{bz+a}$

This formulation enables modeling realistic viewpoint variations see Figure 2.

The abstract transformer over approximates the set of all transformed contours, enabling sound robustness guarantees.

Figure 2. Projective transformation of a contour induced by the rigid motion of a bat in 3D space for DNN certification.

2.2 Contour Reparameterization

Projective transformations induce non-uniform distortions along contour parameterization. This directly impacts abstract bound precision. We compare two strategies **Arc-Length Reparameterization**[6] :

$$\Gamma^*(s) = [x(\phi^{-1}(s)), y(\phi^{-1}(s))]^T \quad (2)$$

with $\phi(t) = \int_0^t |I'(u)| du$. This ensures uniform sampling along the contour.

Affine Reparameterization[7] :

$$\ell = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^t |\det(\Gamma'(u), \Gamma''(u))|^{1/3} du \quad (3)$$

2.3 AI3D system for multimodal DNN verification

The proposed multimodal system verifies deep learning classifiers by jointly leveraging pixel and contour information Figure 1. A projective attack is first applied within a bounded perturbation interval to generate transformed images, from which contours are extracted and reparameterized using affine arc-length to build corresponding abstract domains. The image and contour abstractions are then combined with their respective DNN classifiers within the DeepPoly framework, extended to handle both modalities. An input is certified by AI3D only if robustness is satisfied

across pixel and contour representations, ensuring classifier resilience. In Table 2 we consider the models being used in the case of contours as input data undergoing an arc-length parametrization or an affine arc length one. Our analysis shows that affine reparameterization reduces geometric stretching effects in the abstract domain.

3 Experimental Evaluation

Contours are preprocessed using both arc-length and affine reparameterization before training contour-based DNN classifiers.

Dataset	Model	Type	#Layers	Accuracy for Arc-length	Accuracy for Affine Arc-length
MPEG7	1Conv	Convolutional	4	70%	72.5%
	1Conv_MaxPool	Convolutional	5	70.5%	73.43%
	2Conv	Convolutional	5	74.5%	74.23 %
	2Conv_MaxPool	Convolutional	6	74.5%	73.81%
MNIST	1Conv	Convolutional	4	92.4%	95.11 %
	1Conv_MaxPool	Conv	5	93.7%	95.89%
	2Conv	Conv	5	90.1%	92.18%
	2Conv_MaxPool	Convolutional	6	91.7%	91.4%

Table 2. Different Deep Neural Network architectures for **contour** classification

Robustness is evaluated on two distinct datasets, 100 contours from the MPEG-7 dataset and 100 contours extracted from MNIST. We apply bounded 3D rotation attacks followed by perspective projection and compute certified regions using our extended DeepPoly analyzer.

4 Conclusion

This paper introduces a formal certification framework for contour based object recognition under realistic 3D-2D projective attacks. By modeling transformations through $PSL(2, \mathbb{C})$ and extending DeepPoly to geometric perturbations, we provide solid robustness guarantees. A key contribution of this work is showing that affine contour reparameterization substantially improves certification tightness compared to arc-length normalization. We further extend certification to fully multimodal image-contour networks, develop tighter geometric abstract domains, and explore higher-order projective invariants. Future research directions include the development of new reparameterization techniques for more complex transformations, as well as the optimization of upper and lower bounds within the abstract interpretation framework.

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